

Effect of ionic strength on adsorption of lead in soils of Aligarh district

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Abstract : Adsorption of lead in presence of different concentrations of NaCl and CaCl₂ for evaluating the effect of ionic strength of supporting electrolyte was studied on six different samples of Aligarh district at 25 ± 1 °C. The adsorption of lead increased with the increase in ionic strength of supporting electrolyte solution. The adsorption was more in the presence of NaCl as compared to CaCl₂. The adsorption data conformed to the Freundlich adsorption equation. Freundlich constant (*K*) and the distribution coefficient (*K_d*) supports the above inferences.

Keywords : Lead adsorption, ionic strength, Freundlich adsorption isotherms.

Recent literature have showed that soils irrigated with water containing industrial effluents in big, as well as, in smaller cities are highly polluted with heavy metals, including lead, which require clean up operations¹. Heavy metals added to agricultural soils are retained by adsorption on soil colloidal surfaces such as clay, organic matter, iron and aluminium oxides. Accordingly adsorption of such heavy metals in soil depends on its clay content, pH, CEC, CaCO₃, organic matter and ionic strength of supporting electrolytes². The objective of the present study was to examine Pb adsorption by six different types of soils in presence of various solution species viz. NaCl and CaCl₂, which might occur in industrial and municipal wastes.

Results and discussion

Amount of lead adsorbed by soils at various ionic strengths versus equilibrium concentration (Fig. 1) showed that adsorption isotherms were 'L' shaped in all the soils evaluated at different ionic strengths. The 'L' type isotherms indicate that the adsorbate has a reasonably high relative affinity for the exchanger may be due to minimum competition offered by the solvent for sites on the adsorbing surface. The initial curvature at L-shaped isotherms depends on the rate of change of site availability with increase in solute adsorbed. The slope of isotherm steadily decreases with rise in solute concentration since vacant sites became less accessible due to progressive coverage of the surface³. The adsorption of lead was highest in 1 M NaCl and lowest in 0.01 M CaCl₂·2H₂O amongst all the concentrations of both the supporting electrolyte in all the solutions. The adsorption in presence of NaCl as supportive electrolyte was in the order 1.0 M > 0.1 M > 0.01 M while in presence of CaCl₂ as supportive electrolyte the order was 1.0 M > 0.033 M > 0.01 M. The data (Fig. 1) also denoted that

Fig. 1. Effect of ionic strength of supporting electrolyte on lead adsorption on soil 1 : (●) 1 M NaCl, (×) 0.1 M NaCl, (○) 0.01 M NaCl (Δ) 1 M CaCl₂, (◐) 0.033 M CaCl₂, (▲) 0.01 M CaCl₂.

the adsorption of lead in different soils in presence of different concentrations of NaCl and CaCl₂ followed the order soil No. 1 > 2 > 3 > 4 > 5 > 6.

Higher ionic strength of the electrolyte caused a decrease in thickness of the diffuse layer, thereby decreasing the volume of inner solution which results in reduction of lead adsorption; by increasing the NaCl concentration at a given pH the negative charge of the edge surfaces of the platelates was

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Table 1. Characteristics of soils

Sample no.	Place	Taxonomical name	Soil units	Silt (%)	Clay (%)	pH (1 : 2 : 5)	Organic C (%)	CaCO ₃ (%)	CEC [Cmol (P ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	Surface area (m ² g ⁻¹)	Major clay minerals
1.	Hathras	Entisol	Typic Ustochrept	38.8	16.2	7.8	0.88	6.3	12.8	38.6	Q,I,C
2.	Sikandra Rao	Acidisol	Typic Arigids	52.0	14.0	8.8	0.72	7.6	11.6	36.2	Q,I,C
3.	Datawali	Aridisol	Typic Orthids	37.5	12.0	7.4	0.63	5.8	10.8	30.1	Q,M,I,C
4.	Khair	Aridisol	Typic Orthids	44.9	13.6	7.6	0.56	6.6	10.3	27.2	Q,I,C
5.	Atrauli	Aftisol	Calciorthents	24.9	9.8	8.3	0.44	8.8	9.9	32.1	Q,I,K,C
6.	Bank of Yamuna Tappal	Inceptisol	Calciorthents	27.1	8.5	8.1	0.48	9.0	8.6	25.6	Q,I,K,C

increased⁴. With increase in ionic strength the amount of lead adsorbed increases and may be due to the negative electric field as the main factor which control lead adsorption on soils.

Lead adsorption capacity of a given soil also depends on the ionic composition of the supporting electrolyte. As 0.1 M NaCl and 0.033 M CaCl₂.2H₂O solutions have same ionic strength, but adsorption was higher in 0.1 M NaCl solution as compared to 0.033 M CaCl₂.2H₂O, thereby suggesting more competition by Ca²⁺ for adsorption sites than Na⁺ which causes decrease in adsorption⁵. The divalent cation might increase the positive charge near the sorbent surface which increases electrostatic repulsion between Pb²⁺ and the surface. Surface area was other important factor which governs the adsorption of heavy metal in presence of different cations⁶.

Freundlich adsorption equation :

The adsorption data for the soils studied (with correlation coefficient 0.89–0.98) are given in Table 2. The values of the Freundlich adsorption constant *K* were in the order 1.0 M > 0.1 M > 0.01 M for different soils when NaCl was supporting electrolyte and in the order 1.0 M > 0.033 M > 0.01 M when CaCl₂ was the supporting electrolytes. The values Freundlich constant (*K*) denote that the adsorption capacity of a soil at unit equilibrium concentration of lead increased with the increase in ionic strength. The values of Freundlich constant '*K*' were higher with NaCl as compared to CaCl₂ (of same molarity) indicating a higher adsorption capacity of lead for a soil in presence of NaCl than CaCl₂. The values of 1/*n* during all the studies were less than unity (Table 2) as only a small portion of the theoretically available soil surface is available

Table 2. Effect of ionic strength and nature of supporting electrolyte on Freundlich constants during lead adsorption on soils

Soil no.	NaCl (M)						CaCl ₂ .2H ₂ O (M)					
	0.01		0.1		1.0		0.01		0.033		1.0	
	<i>K</i> *	1/ <i>n</i>	<i>K</i> *	1/ <i>n</i>	<i>K</i> *	1/ <i>n</i>	<i>K</i> *	1/ <i>n</i>	<i>K</i> *	1/ <i>n</i>	<i>K</i> *	1/ <i>n</i>
1.	54.3 (0.8)	0.829 (0.002)	59.9 (0.7)	0.838 (0.002)	64.5 (0.8)	0.856 (0.001)	36.5 (0.7)	0.809 (0.001)	41.5 (0.9)	0.824 (0.002)	47.4 (0.7)	0.842 (0.003)
2.	52.2 (0.6)	0.810 (0.002)	57.2 (0.8)	0.826 (0.002)	60.2 (0.7)	0.843 (0.002)	33.1 (0.6)	0.800 (0.002)	37.4 (0.8)	0.812 (0.002)	41.6 (0.7)	0.826 (0.002)
3.	50.6 (0.7)	0.802 (0.002)	55.6 (0.7)	0.814 (0.004)	58.9 (0.9)	0.832 (0.003)	31.3 (0.7)	0.786 (0.003)	35.2 (0.6)	0.802 (0.002)	38.6 (0.8)	0.812 (0.002)
4.	48.9 (0.7)	0.790 (0.002)	53.6 (0.8)	0.802 (0.002)	56.2 (0.7)	0.820 (0.002)	29.4 (0.7)	0.770 (0.002)	33.1 (0.6)	0.784 (0.004)	31.2 (0.7)	0.800 (0.002)
5.	46.7 (0.5)	0.770 (0.002)	50.9 (0.7)	0.790 (0.002)	54.2 (0.8)	0.812 (0.002)	27.2 (0.6)	0.752 (0.003)	30.8 (0.7)	0.764 (0.002)	28.9 (0.8)	0.782 (0.004)
6.	44.8 (0.6)	0.750 (0.002)	49.1 (0.6)	0.777 (0.004)	51.4 (0.5)	0.800 (0.003)	26.3 (0.4)	0.740 (0.002)	29.4 (0.8)	0.754 (0.001)	27.3 (0.6)	0.766 (0.004)

The values in parentheses show standard error of estimate.

*Unit of *K* = mg^{1-1/n} L^{1/n} kg⁻¹.

for adsorption⁶. The values of $1/n$ (Table 2) were in the order $1.0 M > 0.1 M > 0.01 M$ for NaCl and $1.0 M > 0.033 M > 0.01 M$ for $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Table 2 also denotes that adsorption of lead in presence of different electrolyte and at different ionic strength followed the order soil No. $1 > 2 > 3 > 4 > 5 > 6$.

The values of K_d (distribution coefficient) calculated as :

$$K_d (\text{mL g}^{-1}) = \frac{X/m (\mu\text{g g}^{-1})}{C (\mu\text{g mL}^{-1})}$$

were in the same order as that of the Freundlich constant i.e. $1.0 M > 0.1 M > 0.01 M$ of NaCl and $1.0 M > 0.033 M > 0.01 M$ of CaCl_2 , supporting the above inferences.

From these data, i.e. adsorption isotherms, the Freundlich constants K , $1/n$ and distribution coefficient it may be concluded that lead adsorption on soils of Aligarh district was not only influenced by ionic strength of supporting electrolyte but also by the type of cation species. Sorption of Pb by sewage sludge irrigated soils may be greatly influenced by the cationic composition of the leachate and deposition of these cations in soils.

Materials and methods :

Six surface soils (0–30 cm; 1–6) from different parts of Aligarh district which were not irrigated by sewage water were collected and sieved through 100 mesh sieve. Physicochemical properties were determined by standard methods and are given in Table 1⁷. To evaluate the effect of ionic strength of NaCl and $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ on lead adsorption, 2 g soil samples were equilibrated with 25 mL of electrolyte containing (0, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 80, 100, 120, 140, 160, 180, 200 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of lead) for 24 h at 25 ± 1 °C with constant shaking. After equilibrium the samples were centrifuged for 5 min at 4000 rpm. Lead concentration in supernatant was estimated by

atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The amount of lead adsorbed was determined from the difference between the amount of lead added and left out in the equilibrium solution.

Data pertaining to the adsorption of lead were fitted to Freundlich equation : $\log X/m = \log K + 1/n \log C$ where X/m is amount of lead adsorbed mg g^{-1} soil, C is equilibrium concentration of lead (mg mL^{-1}), K and $1/n$ are the Freundlich constants. Plot of $\log X/m$ vs $\log C$ is a straight line with slope of $1/n$ and intercept $\log K$. Values for ' K ' represented the amount of lead adsorbed at unit equilibrium concentration and $1/n$ indicated the degree of linearity between solution equilibrium concentration and adsorption⁸.

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